

Synthetic Experiments on Pongamol

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A number of new pyrazole and isoxazole derivatives have been synthesised starting from pongamol a naturally occurring benzofuran derivative containing 1,3-diketone system. All the compounds have been characterised by their analytical and spectral data and were screened for their antifeedant activity.

In our earlier communications^{1,2}, we reported the isolation of pongamol (1), a benzofuran derivative possessing 1,3-diketone system, from *Tephrosia hamiltonii* in good yields. A number of pyrazoles³ and isoxazoles⁴ are known to exhibit a variety of physiological activities. Therefore, the synthesis of some new pyrazole and isoxazole derivatives starting from pongamol (1) was undertaken with a view to evaluate their antifeedant activity.

Pongamol (1) on heating with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of glacial acetic acid yielded 3-[5'-(4'-methoxybenzofuranyl)]-5-phenylpyrazole (2).

Biological activities of substituted acrylophenones were attributed to the presence of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl groups⁵⁻⁸. Independently, 1,3-diketones are also known to exhibit a variety of biological activities⁹. If both α,β -unsaturated ketone and 1,3-diketone systems are present in the same compounds, they may be expected to exhibit better physiological activity. Keeping this objective in mind, the synthesis of some substituted acrylophenones from pongamol and their conversion into the corresponding 3,4,5-trisubstituted-pyrazoles (4a-d) was taken up (Scheme 1) and the results are presented.

Condensation of pongamol (1) with benzaldehyde, 2-chloro- and 4-methyl benzaldehydes in the presence of piperidine yielded the corresponding 2-[5'-(4'-methoxybenzofuranyl)]-3-arylacrylophenones (3a-c).

Pongamol (1) on condensation with *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde in the presence of piperidine did not yield the expected compound (3e) but gave a demethylated acrylophenone (3d), which was characterised as 2-[5'-(4'-methoxybenzofuranyl)]-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acrylophenone (3d) on the basis of analytical and spectral data. The structure of the product was unambiguously confirmed by its synthesis from pongamol and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde in the presence of piperidine.

The acrylophenones (3a-c) were condensed with excess of hydrazine hydrate in the presence of glacial acetic acid to yield corresponding 3-[5'-(4'-methoxybenzofuranyl)]-4-arylidine-5-phenylpyrazoles (4a-c).

The acrylophenone (3d) on condensation with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of glacial acetic acid yielded a colourless compound (4d) which was soluble in 2% aqueous alkali and gave green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. The product on acetylation with Ac₂O/pyridine at room temperature formed a diacetate, m.p. 158°, and *M*⁺ 464 in mass spectrum confirmed the presence of two hydroxyl groups. Further, ¹H nmr spectrum of the diacetate showed two separate signals at δ 2.80 (3H, s) and 2.20 (3H, s) indicating the presence of two acetoxy groups in the acetate (4f) and thereby two hydroxyl groups in 4d. Therefore, 4d was characterised as 3-[5'-(4'-hydroxybenzofuranyl)]-4-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-phenyl pyrazole.

Condensation of pongamol (1) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of glacial acetic acid yielded an isoxazole derivative (5).

Antifeedant activity: All the compounds were tested for antifeedant activity following the 'non-choice method'¹⁰ using 6 h prestarved fourth instar larvae of *Spodoptera litura* F. The compounds 2, 3b, 4b and 4d exhibited highest antifeedant activity (Table 1). It is interesting to mention that compounds derived from pongamol exhibited relatively higher antifeedant activity than pongamol.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Completion of the reaction and purity of the compounds were checked by tlc.

3-[5'-(4'-Methoxybenzofuranyl)]-5-phenylpyrazole (2): A 15% hydrazine hydrate (5.0 ml) was added dropwise to pongamol (1; 0.35 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5.0 ml) and the mixture was gently heated for 10 min at water-bath temperature. It was then cooled to room temperature and was diluted with water. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (0.3 g), m.p. 164-65°, C₁₈H₁₄O₂N₂ (*M*⁺ 290); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 260 (N-H), 1 610 (C=C), 1 560 (C=N) and 1 232 (C-O), 1 160, 1 050 cm⁻¹ (benzofuran moiety)¹¹; λ_{max} (EtOH) (log ϵ) 206.5 (4.21), 234 (4.37) and 280 (3.68)¹²;

Scheme 1

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND ANTIFEEDANT ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Antifeedant activity %
2	164-5	87	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	90.0
3a	136	83	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₄	20.9
3b	140-41	87	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ O ₄ Cl	93.6
3c	100	67	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₄	nil
3d	130	78	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₅	60.5
4a	162	72	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂	30.6
4b	173	67	C ₂₅ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₂ Cl	97.3
4c	167	68	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₂	20.6
4d	174	70	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₂	96.2
5	102	60.6	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂ N	40.8

*All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

δ (60 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.07 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-3')¹³, 7.37 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, H-2')¹³, 7.23 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-7'), 7.60 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6'), 7.33 (3H, m, H-3'', 4'', 5''), 7.83 (2H, m, H-2'', 6''), 6.83 (1H, s, H-4)¹⁴; *m/z* (rel. int. %) *M*⁺ 290

(100), 275 (90), 261 (11), 247 (7), 189 (12), 186 (8) and 159 (7).

2-[5'-(4'-Methoxybenzofuranoyl)]-3-arylacrylophenones (3a-c). *General procedure*: To a mixture of pongamol (1; 0.01 mol) and the aromatic aldehyde (0.012 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), a few drops of piperidine was added and heated (80°) over a water-bath for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to 5° and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from methanol to yield the corresponding acrylophenones (3a-c) in good yields: 3b C₂₅H₁₇O₄Cl; ν_{max} (KBr) 1660, 1600 (α,β-unsaturated C=O) and 1160, 1050 cm⁻¹ (benzofuran moiety)¹¹; λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) 213 (4.50), 238 (4.30) and 303 nm (4.38); δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.10 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.89 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-3')¹³, 7.70 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-2')¹³, 8.13 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6'), 7.43 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-7'), 7.59 (3H, m, H-2'', 3'', 6''), 7.30 (7H, m, H-3'', 4'', 5'', 4'', 5'', 6''); *m/z* (rel. int. %) *M*⁺ 416 (1), 312 (50), 277 (100), 241 (8), 175 (95), 105 (10) and 77 (20).

Condensation of pongamol (1) with 4-methoxybenzaldehyde: Pongamol (1; 0.29 g) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) was treated with 4-methoxybenzaldehyde (0.15 g) and a few drops of piperidine. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 4.5 h. The solution was then concentrated to a small volume. The solid that separated was washed and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (0.31 g), m.p. 130°. It gave light wine colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. The product was characterised as 2-[5'-(4'-methoxybenzofuranoyl)]-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acrylophenone (3d) on the basis of spectral evidence: ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 500 (non-chelated OH), 3 100 (chelated OH)¹⁵, 1 645 (C=O), 1 600 (C=C), 1 580, 1 570, 1 528 (aromatic C=C), 1 140 and 1 065 (benzofuran moiety); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 224 (4.57), 263.5 (4.58), 299 (4.54); δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 3.80 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.12 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-3'), 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-2'), 7.45 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-7'), 8.07 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6'), 7.85 (4H, m, H-2'', 2''', 6'', 6'''), 7.35-7.60 (5H, m, H-3'', 3''', 4'', 5'', 5''') and 6.75 (1H, s, H-3). The mass spectrum of 3d did not show *M*⁺ at 398, which is the behaviour of highly substituted organic compounds, however, the spectrum displayed all important fragment ions as required by the assigned structure at *m/z* 262 (72), 234 (8), 160 (100), 134 (32), 131 (15), 117 (10), 103 (7) and 77 (12). The fragment ion at *m/z* 117 arising due to *p*-hydroxystyryl cation also supported our observation that the methoxy group located at C-4'' position underwent demethylation during the course of the reaction.

Authentic synthesis of 3d: A mixture of pongamol (1; 0.1 g), *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (0.06 g) and a few drops of piperidine dissolved in ethanol was heated on a water-bath for 4.5 h. The solution was then concentrated to a small volume. The resulting solid was washed and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (0.05 g), m.p. 130°. The product (3d) was found to be identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., superimposable ir) with the product obtained from the reaction of pongamol and *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde.

3-[5'-(4'-Methoxybenzofuranyl)]-4-arylidine-5-phenylpyrazoles (4a-c). **General procedure:** A mixture of acrylophenone (0.01 mol) and 15% hydrazine hydrate (excess) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 30 min. It was then diluted with the water and the resulting solid was washed, dried and crystallised from methanol in good yields. The products did not form 2,4-DNP derivative indicating the absence of carbonyl group and gave prussian blue colour in Lassaigne's test for nitrogen: 4b C₂₅H₁₇O₂N₂Cl, *M*⁺ 412; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 650 (C=C), 1 590 (C=N), 1 140 and 1 053 cm⁻¹ (benzofuran moiety); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 214 (4.44), 238 (4.49), 256 (4.33), 298 (3.69) and 307 (3.64); δ (90 MHz, CDCl₃) 4.04 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.0 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-3'), 7.28 (7H, m, H- α , 3'', 4'', 4''', 5'', 5''' and 6''), 7.48 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-7'), 7.62 (4H, m, H-2', 2'', 3'', 6''), 7.88 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6'); *m/z* (rel. int. %) 368 (35), 333 (15), 324 (100), 277 (32), 189 (22), 175 (97) and 160 (43).

3-[5'-(4'-Hydroxybenzofuranyl)]-4-(4-hydroxybenzylidene)-5-phenylpyrazole (4d): To a solution of 3d (0.15 g) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml), 15 hydrazine hydrate (excess) was added dropwise and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 1 h. It was then cooled to room temperature, diluted with water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (0.1 g), m.p. 174°, C₂₄H₁₆O₃N₂; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 370 (non-chelated OH), 3 310 (chelated OH), 1 645 (C=C), 1 600 (C=N), 1 135, 1 050 (benzofuran moiety), 750 and 723 cm⁻¹ (monosubstituted benzene); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 212 (4.33), 237 (4.60), 253 (4.53), 298 (3.88) and 310 (3.84); δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-3'), 7.67 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-2'), 8.10 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-6'), 7.0 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-7'), 7.1-7.60 (9H, m, H-2'', 2''', 3'', 3''', 4'', 5'', 5''', 6'', 6'''), 6.80 (1H, s, H- α) and 7.85 (2H, br D₂O exchangeable, C-4' and 4'' OH); *m/z* (rel. int. %) *M*⁺ 380 (1), 275 (40), 262 (70), 238 (8), 160 (100), 132 (13), 117 (10), 104 (8) and 77 (25).

5-[5'-(4'-Methoxybenzofuranyl)]-3-phenylisoxazole (5): To pongamol (1; 0.2 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was added hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.1 g). The mixture was heated at 80° for 1 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water and the resulting dark coloured solid was washed and crystallised from methanol as cream coloured needles (0.12 g), m.p. 102°, C₁₈H₁₃O₃N; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 645 (C=C), 1 600 (C=N), 1 565, 1 500, 1 480 (aromatic C=C), 1 188, 1 070 (benzofuran moiety), 732 and 710 (monosubstituted benzene); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 210 (4.19), 237 (4.38) and 272 (4.13) characteristic of isoxazoles¹⁶; δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.21 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.03 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-3), 7.62 (1H, d, *J* 2.25 Hz, H-2), 7.05 (1H, s, H-4), 7.89 (3H, m, H-2', 6'', 6'''), 7.45 (4H, m, H-3'', 4'', 5'', 7'); *m/z* (rel. int. %) *M*⁺ 291 (100), 262 (15), 214 (15), 186 (27), 175 (71), 172 (21), 160 (26), 158 (10), 144 (7), 116 (10), 104 (50) and 77 (38).

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